

NONDESTRUCTIVE INSPECTION AND MECHANICAL TESTING OF COMPOSITE ARM BOOMS FOR THE SPACE STATION REMOTE MANIPULATOR SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

This paper outlines the phases of testing and verification of the Space Station Remote Manipulator System (SSRMS) arm booms completed to date. Material selection, processing technique, description of the arm boom components and testing performed to evaluate the structural integrity of engineering model specimens as well as full size model specimens are presented. Emphasis is placed on the immersion C-Scan procedures for ultrasonic inspection and the mechanical test procedures to measure arm boom strength and stiffness.

INTRODUCTION

The Mobile Servicing System (MSS) is Canada's contribution to the International Space Station Alpha. It will be used for the assembly and maintenance of the Space Station, for transfer of equipment and supplies around the Station, release and capture of satellites, support of astronauts working in space and for servicing instruments and other payloads attached to the Space Station. One of the major components of the MSS is the next generation Canadarm or Space Station Remote Manipulator System (SSRMS). The SSRMS general arrangement is shown in Fig. 1. It is being built under the direction of the Canadian Space Agency, with SPAR Aerospace as its prime contractor. Under contract to SPAR Aerospace, FRE Composites is responsible for the design and manufacture of the composite arm booms of the SSRMS, and for the design of the metallic flanges and the electronic mounts. In collaboration with FRE Composites, the Institute for Aerospace Research of the National Research Council of Canada is performing nondestructive inspection and mechanical testing of engineering and qualification versions of the arm booms.

Figure 1. SSRMS Arm Boom Arrangement

The SSRMS testing plan encompasses five phases of testing and verification of the SSRMS arm booms including: 1) Development Phase Testing, 2) Engineering Model Phase Testing (0.6 m long composite tube), 3) SSTA (Test Article) Full Size Model Phase Testing (6.6 m long test specimen), 4) Qualification Phase Testing (6.6 m long test specimen and brackets) and 5) Flight Phase Testing.

Phases one and two are complete. The first phase consisted of material selection and development of a processing technique for the SSRMS arm booms. The second phase, Engineering Model Phase Testing, consisted of subjecting three engineering model specimens to acceptance loads.

SSTA Full Size Model Phase Testing, currently underway, consists of subjecting two full size model specimens (SSTA boom assemblies) to *acceptance* loads (launching loads) to determine tube torsional and bending stiffnesses and to verify that tube strength attains minimum allowable values. Ultrasonic C-Scan inspection is performed before and after mechanical testing to verify conformance to requirements.

Qualification Phase Testing consists of subjecting one full size model (Qualification boom assembly) specimen to higher magnitude *qualification* loads (launching loads with safety factors) to determine tube torsional and bending stiffnesses and to verify that tube strength attains minimum allowable values. Tests will be performed both before and after exposure to thermal cycling. Ultrasonic C-Scan inspection is also performed before and after mechanical testing and thermal exposure to verify conformance to requirements. In addition, ancillary mounting brackets that will be attached to this qualification boom assembly will be evaluated on the basis of strength, stiffness and fatigue. The last phase, Flight Phase Testing, will consist of flight acceptance testing of three boom assemblies (full size configuration arm boom).

This paper outlines procedures and results of the first three phases of testing. Emphasis is placed on the immersion C-Scan procedures for ultrasonic inspection and the unique mechanical test procedures to measure arm boom strength and stiffness in torsion and bending currently being carried out at the NRC.

DEVELOPMENT PHASE TESTING

MATERIAL SELECTION AND COMPOSITE BOOM FABRICATION

Weight saving, overall stiffness and strength are driving factors in the design of most space structures. Other major design requirements include resistance to environmental factors such as atomic oxygen, vacuum, radiation, thermal cycling, and space debris. The low Earth orbit space environment in which the MSS will operate for thirty years has been proven to be very hostile and materials resistant to this harsh environment are required [1].

For the SSRMS, strength is an overriding design consideration due to the magnitude of loads applied to the arm booms while in a folded configuration during launch. Consequently, high strength carbon fibre, ICI Fiberite IM7, was selected. A comprehensive literature survey led to the selection of two candidate materials based on IM7 fibre for the boom design: IM7/977-2, a carbon fibre reinforced epoxy composite and IM7/PEEK, a carbon fibre reinforced thermoplastic composite. The two candidate materials were then subjected to a comparative evaluation based on tensile, compression and shear testing, as well as environmental testing such as thermal cycling, resistance to atomic oxygen bombardment and radiation, emissivity and outgassing. Since the composite tube / metallic flange interface is the critical area, quasi static tensile and fatigue testing of breadboard bolted joint coupons were also conducted. Results of these tests led to the selection of IM7/PEEK for fabrication of the SSRMS arm booms due to its superior performance [2]. After these tests, a study of flaw growth and crack propagation in the selected material was performed.

The required number of plies and the ply orientation of the carbon/PEEK seamless tube were determined so as to meet strength, stiffness and process requirements with minimum weight. Computer optimization software developed by FRE Composites was utilized. Critical locations such as the tube/metallic flange interfaces were analyzed with the PATRAN finite element package.

FRE Composites developed a processing technique to manually lay-up the rigid non-tacky unidirectional fibre/matrix tape around a steel mandrel. Nineteen plies are laid up around the steel mandrel with twenty-three more plies added at each end of the tube to form a built-up section. The consolidation of the composite tube is done in an autoclave based on the manufacturer's specified curing cycle of 393°C at 0.7 MPa.

ENGINEERING MODEL PHASE TESTING

The Engineering Model Phase Testing consisted of subjecting three engineering model (EM) specimens to qualification bending and torsion loads, to validate the design with respect to lamination and the flange to composite bolted interface, as well as to establish the performance of the design and to qualify the fabrication process. Each specimen consisted of a 0.6 m long composite tube, 35.6 cm in diameter with metallic rings attached at each end. The EM specimens were tested to failure after being subjected to launch qualification loads, thermal cycling (four cycles between -151°C and 111°C) and ground impact loads (6.8 Joules impact). The EM specimens failed at an average bending moment of 78,500 Nm [2]. Results from these tests showed that 1) static strength, local wall stability and bending and torsional stiffnesses met specifications when EM specimens were subjected to maximum

qualification load levels, 2) static strength, local wall stability and bending and torsional stiffness specifications were met after thermal cycling and 3) specified impacts did not cause significant damage to the specimen.

SSTA FULL SIZE MODEL PHASE TESTING

The SSTA Full Size Model Phase Testing, which is currently underway, consists of subjecting two full size model specimens (SSTA boom assemblies) to acceptance loads to determine tube torsional and bending stiffnesses and to verify the minimum allowable tube strength. Each specimen or boom assembly consists of two 3.0 m long, 35.6 cm diameter composite tubes connected by a hinge mechanism. Ultrasonic C-Scan inspection is performed before and after mechanical testing to verify conformance to requirements. At this time, torsional and bending stiffnesses have been determined for boom assembly B1-B2 (see Fig. 1) and the tube strength in bending has been verified to the minimum allowable value for boom segment B1 only.

FULL SIZE BOOM COMPONENTS

The full size boom assembly was designed based on the analysis and test results from the EM units. Boom components include the composite segment, pitch and hinge flanges, electronic mounts and ground plane. The laminated tube including the reinforcement built-up for the flange/composite interface, is identical to the one used in the EM, except that its length is increased from 0.6 m to 3.0 m. The flanges are machined from 7075-T6 aluminum forgings and are assembled to the boom in a vertical position. A ground plane made from 1145-H19 0.076 mm thick aluminum foil, anodized with chromic acid, is adhesively bonded to the surface of the boom. The aluminum foil follows the routing of the cable supports that will be installed along the booms. Seven different electronic mounts that will support electronic/electrical units will be attached to the SSRMS (2 ACUs, 2 VDUs, BCU, 2 Support Brackets; see Fig. 1). These attachments are designed by FRE Composites and will be installed on the qualification boom in the next testing phase. For the SSTA boom assemblies, seven equivalent masses are attached to the boom in place of the electronic mounts. The total evaluated weight of boom segments A1, A2, B1 and B2, including composite tubes, flanges, electronic mounts, ground plane and hardware, is 168 kg. The composite tubes alone weigh between 14 and 15 kg.

NONDESTRUCTIVE INSPECTION

To verify the integrity of the arm booms for the SSRMS, an ultrasonic C-scan inspection is performed at specific stages of the production and testing phases. The inspection is accomplished through a reflection pulse/echo technique in a 3.6 m long by 1.2 m wide by 1.2 m deep immersion tank. The composite segment rests horizontally in the immersion tank on a bar stock indexer as shown in Fig. 2. The scanning portion of the mechanism with its alignment manipulator and ultrasonic transducer scan the length of the test specimen from the outside of the test specimen tube assembly while the tube is indexed about its centre axis by the bar stock indexer. A single 5MHz piezoelectric transducer is used for sending and receiving the ultrasonic signal. This frequency provides the resolution to reliably detect anomalies of the specified size. A reflector bar is placed inside the tube and each end of the bar is adjusted to ensure that it is parallel to the inner surface of the tube and to obtain a

maximum response from the transducer. The area being inspected is submerged during testing and the tube is scanned a full length and then indexed for the next pass. The tube is scanned at a speed of 152mm/s, and is indexed in 2 mm increments.

Figure 2. Ultrasonic C-scan Inspection Set Up

Flaws and voids are identified by the attenuation of the received ultrasonic signal. An area showing a received signal less than 25% of the full screen height is considered to be a flaw or void. The evaluation of the integrity of the built-up steps section is somewhat different than on the uniform composite shell. In the built-up taper region, the ultrasonic transducer is not oriented normal to the part, due to the change in geometry (steps of the built-up from the laminate shell to the top of the built-up section). This may result in signal losses of up to 80% due to the reflection and scatter. The signal scatter ceases if the ultrasonic transducer is re-oriented normal to the part at the top of the built-up. Additional C-Scans are therefore performed on the built-up steps section by adjusting the signal perpendicular to the section.

The resolution of the C-scan must be capable of detecting defects including voids, delaminations, cracks and inclusions larger than 6.4 mm by 6.4 mm embedded in the composite material. All flaws and voids were deemed acceptable or rejected per the following specification on the flaw size and flaw density:

- i) Acceptable Flaw Size: $\leq 12.7 \text{ mm} \times \leq 12.7 \text{ mm}$; $\leq 6.4 \text{ mm} \times \leq 38.1 \text{ mm}$;
 $\leq (6.4 \text{ mm to } 12.7 \text{ mm}) \times \leq (12.7 \text{ mm to } 38.1 \text{ mm})$ if surface area is $\leq 242 \text{ mm}^2$; $< 6.4 \text{ mm}$ if surface area is $\leq 242 \text{ mm}^2$.
- ii) Acceptable Flaw Density: $\text{FDF} \leq 0.5$. The FDF is determined by dividing the maximum flaw dimension of the larger flaw by the distance between the two flaws.

The first inspection of a boom segment takes place after the boom is consolidated. If anomalies larger than the minimum are detected in the composite at this stage, a second consolidation is done, which in most cases will eliminate the majority of anomalies. A reconsolidation would not have been possible if an epoxy based composite had been selected. Another ultrasonic inspection is performed to ensure that the anomalies have indeed been

eliminated. Occasionally, a third consolidation is necessary. Ultrasonic inspection is also performed after each mechanical test and thermal cycling exposure.

Small surface wrinkles in the composite measuring approximately 0.4 mm height and 0.8 mm in width and visible with the unaided eye diffused some of the acoustical energy producing images that look very much like true anomalies. Several of these were sectioned and investigated by SEM. Some of the wrinkles did have microscopic voids in their interiors, but the size of these voids were well below the minimum specified, and are too small to affect the strength of the boom.

MECHANICAL TESTING

Stiffness Tests

Boom assembly B1-B2 has been subjected to separately applied torsional and bending moments during which displacements were measured to determine tube torsional and bending stiffnesses. The test rig consisted of two main fixtures anchored to the floor. The test set-up for the torsional and bending moment application is shown schematically in Fig. 3. One actuator was used to apply load through a 0.457 m long arm to generate torsional moment. Two actuators were used to apply loads through 0.762 m moment arms to generate bending moments at each end of the test specimen. The load applied by each of the three actuators was controlled by an MTS Flex Test/T/RAC DSC controller using feedback outputs from load cells placed between hydraulic actuators and the moment arms.

Figure 3. Schematic of the Test Rig for the Stiffness Tests

Applied loads were measured by load cells mounted directly to the hydraulic actuators. Induced secondary torsion loads were measured with a load cell mounted at the end of the torque reaction arm. Six digital displacement indicators located along the boom assembly were used to measure vertical deflection of the arm boom under bending load while one

digital displacement indicator measured any lateral movement of the boom. Two dual axis inclinometers mounted on the test fixture interfaces were used to measure angular rotation of the arm booms under torsional loading. A non-contact electro-optical displacement follower was used to provide back-up displacement measurement under bending load. A high speed data acquisition system was used to record load and displacement data.

A relatively insignificant load of approximately 80 N was sensed by the torsion reaction load cell at the maximum applied bending load during the bending test. The maximum displacement measured at tube mid length during the bending tests was 10.4 mm while the maximum angular displacement measured during torsion loading tests was 0.34°. Using classical beam theory, bending stiffness was calculated from bending moment and displacement data obtained during the bending stiffness test. Torsional stiffness was calculated from torsional moment and angular displacement data during the torsional stiffness test. The measured bending and torsional stiffness values of $EI = 3.56 \times 10^6 \text{ Nm}^6$ and $GJ = 2.56 \times 10^6 \text{ Nm}^6$, respectively, are above the specification requirements.

Strength Test

It was determined that the hinge mechanism connecting the two composite tube segments would not stand the bending acceptance loads for the tubes. Therefore the minimum allowable strength and local wall stability could not be verified on a boom assembly but only on a single segment strength test. At this time, only boom segment B1 has been subjected to bending acceptance loads.

The test set-up for the bending moment application is shown schematically in Fig. 4.

Figure 4. Schematic of the Test Rig for the Strength Tests

The single segment test rig consisted of two main fixtures, the Right Hand Side Frame Assembly and a Reaction Shackle, both of which were anchored to the floor. The load applied by the hydraulic actuator was controlled by an MTS Flex Test/T/RAC DSC controller using feedback output from a load cell placed between the hydraulic actuator and the test component. The actuator applied loads through a 0.762 m moment arm to generate

a bending moment of 14,900 Nm at the composite/flange interface. The bending moment was derived from the output of a load cell installed in the reaction shackle linkage multiplied by the distance between the composite/flange interface and the reaction shackle.

Although not necessary for the strength tests, displacement measurement devices were installed on the boom. A non-contact electro-optical displacement follower and two dial indicators were used to provide vertical displacement measurements at the loading and reaction points. One inclinometer was mounted to the specimen/moment arm interface to measure induced rotational displacement. The maximum rotational displacement was considered negligible. Specified bending moments at the composite/flange interface were met without causing any visual damage. At the time of writing this paper, no ultrasonic C-scan inspection has been performed to evaluate the structural integrity of the booms after mechanical testing.

CONCLUSION

This paper presented phases of testing and verification of the SSRMS arm booms with an emphasis on the immersion C-Scan procedures for ultrasonic inspection and the mechanical test procedures to measure arm boom strength and stiffness in torsion and bending. Ultrasonic C-scan inspection performed on as fabricated booms showed that it was possible to fabricate a composite tube that conforms to requirements. Results from tests performed to date show that the bending and torsional stiffnesses of the boom assembly B1-B2 met the specifications and that the minimum allowable strength of boom segment B1 was verified. However, no ultrasonic inspection has been done to date to evaluate the structural integrity of the composite tubes after mechanical testing. Before a boom qualifies for flight, other tests must be carried out. These include the determination of bending and torsional stiffnesses, the verification of minimum allowable strength and ultrasonic C-scan inspection, after thermal stress exposure. As well, the strength, stiffness and fatigue evaluation testing of ancillary mounting brackets attached to the qualification boom assembly is required.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work has been performed under a Collaborative Agreement between the Institute for Aerospace Research and FRE Composites Inc., under IAR Program 3H3, Aerospace Materials and Engineering Physics, Project LH3-11. Special thanks go to P. Adams, R. Hewitt and M. Charlesworth from IAR/NRC and M. Fraser from FRE Composites.

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